

Towards Compact Design of Haptic Interfaces for Caress-Like Stimuli

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Abstract—Several studies in the affective haptics research field showed the potentiality of using haptic technology to convey emotions in remote communications. In this context, it is of interest to simplify the haptic feedback without altering the informative content of the stimulus to develop affective haptic devices whose technological complexity is limited and decrease the amount of data to be transmitted in remote haptic interactions.

In this work, we investigated the correlation between the parameters regulating a caress-like stimulation and the perceived pleasantness. A small difference in the pleasantness ratings was observed between caresses provided with linear movements and those given as discrete sequences of taps. The presence of vibration had a little effect on the perceived pleasantness.

I. THE STUDY

Haptics plays a central role for communicating and understanding the emotional state of other people in social, affective, and intimate relationships [1]. When the communication is mediated by haptic technology, the ability to truthfully convey the emotional aspects of social and affective touch is critical for enhancing the feeling of presence.

Among the haptic sensations that can be delivered in the context of mediated affective touch, caress-like stimuli have received a considerable attention. To the best of our knowledge, the interaction between tapping, vibrations, velocity, and temperature in this kind of stimuli has not been systematically investigated yet. Thus, in this paper we propose a careful comparison of different haptic stimuli to identify the best combination for generating a pleasant, caress-like sensation. These results could provide the guidelines to simplify the tactile stimulation in wearable haptics technology while still maintaining the pleasantness of a caress, not only in the interaction between remote human subjects, but also in the human-robot communication domain.

To investigate the interaction between temperature, vibration, and type of motion to deliver a pleasant stimulus resembling a caress, we used the method of adjustment [2] and asked participants to find the most pleasant sensation by tuning a set of parameters considered meaningful for the stimulus at

Fig. 1: The participant is tuning the temperature of the end-effector while his right forearm is stimulated.

hand. Overall, 23 participants took part in two experiments, of which 13 in the first experiment (7 males and 6 females, average age \pm SD: 26.3 ± 3.1), and 10 in the second (3 males and 7 females, average age \pm SD: 27.6 ± 3.1). By using a customized version of the Omega.3 haptic interface (see Fig. 2), we generated two types of motion stimuli: a continuous stroke (linear motion stimulus) and a discrete sequence of taps (rabbit stimulus). The two stimuli were applied to the hairy skin of the forearm of the participant (see Fig. 1). In both stimulus types, linear and rabbit, the distance between the starting position and the ending position of the stimulus was 15 cm, while the force applied by the haptic interface at the contact point was 0.3 N.

The two stimuli were presented with and without vibration of the end-effector, and the vibration frequency was set at 30 Hz. As a result, each experimental session consisted of four conditions tested in four blocks: linear without vibration, linear with vibration, rabbit without vibration, and rabbit with vibration. Each condition consisted of 12 trials, of which six

Fig. 2: The haptic interface adopted to stimulate the participants' forearm. In a), the Omega.3 haptic device with a custom end-effector. In b), the exploded view of the terminal part of the end-effector detailing all the embedded components: a 3D printed support (A), the temperature sensor (B), two fans (C), the heat sink (D), and the Peltier Cell (E). In c), the assembled view of the terminal part of the end-effector.

trials started the stimulation from the elbow and the other six from the wrist, in random order. A similar experimental procedure was tested in two experiments. In the first experiment (Sect. I-A), the velocity of the stimulus was fixed and the participant changed the temperature at the contact point, while in the second experiment (Sect. I-B) the velocity was changed by the participants and the temperature fixed. Each experiment lasted about one hour. Meaningful data were logged with a rate of 100 Hz so that the entire experiment could be played back for the purposes of the analysis.

A. Experiment 1: Temperature

In all trials, the stimulation velocity was fixed and equal to 3 cm s^{-1} , in accordance with [3]. In particular, in the linear modality this velocity coincided with the end-effector linear velocity tangential to the forearm of the participants. For what concerns the rabbit modality, the end-effector tapped the forearm of the participants 5 times with fixed distance between taps equal to 3 cm. The duration of each tap was 100 ms, and the elapsed time between two different taps was 1 s corresponding to a stimulus lateral speed of 3 cm s^{-1} .

The starting temperature was 18°C for half of the trials and 42°C for the other half, randomly selected. The temperature range upper bound was chosen not to harm the participants [4]. Hence, there were four possible trial initial conditions from the combination between two factors: starting temperature (18°C or 42°C) and starting point (wrist side or elbow side). Each combination was presented three times in random order, for a total of 12 trials per condition.

In each trial, the participant was tasked to adjust the temperature of the stimulus. By means of two digital buttons they could augment or decrease the temperature with steps of 1°C , and the temperature change was applied in real time manner. There was no time limit during the trial, and the participant could change the temperature as many times as needed in order to find the most pleasant stimulation. At the end of each trial, participants were asked to rate the pleasantness of the stimulation on a Visual Analog Scale (VAS) from 1 (low pleasantness) to 10 (high pleasantness).

B. Experiment 2: Velocity

In the second experiment, the temperature of the end-effector was fixed and equal to 34°C , i.e. equal to the mean final temperature ($33.93^\circ\text{C} \pm 3.68^\circ\text{C}$) computed among the 624 trials (13 participants, 48 trials each) of the previous experiment, regardless the experimental condition. This time, participants were asked to adjust the velocity of the end-effector to increase the pleasantness of the stimulus as much as possible.

For each experimental condition, half of the trials had a starting speed of 1 cm s^{-1} , while the others had a starting speed of 5 cm s^{-1} , randomly selected. Similarly to the first experiment, the trial initial condition was a combination of starting velocity (1 cm s^{-1} or 5 cm s^{-1}) and starting point (wrist side or elbow side), and each combination was presented three times in random order, for a total of 12 trials per condition.

Participants were able to increase and reduce the end-effector velocity with a step of 0.5 cm s^{-1} , and the velocity changes were applied in real time manner. There were neither time nor number of velocity changes limits. Once the participants confirmed the final end-effector velocity, they were asked to rate the pleasantness of the stimulation on a VAS scale ranging from 1 (low pleasantness) to 10 (high pleasantness).

II. ANALYSIS

We used the Linear Mixed Models (LMM) [5] to perform the analysis. For the first experiment, we analyzed whether the stimulation modality (linear/rabbit) or the presence of vibration predicted the selected temperature and pleasantness rating. The same analyses were performed for the second experiment, setting the selected velocity and the rating as a dependent variable. The R package lem4 was used for LMM fitting to the data [6].

III. RESULTS

A. Experiment 1: Temperature

The first experiment was aimed at finding the temperature perceived as most pleasant by the participants at varying experimental condition. For each trial, final temperature,

Fig. 3: Results of Experiment 1. Final selected temperature and pleasantness ratings divided by experimental condition are reported in a) and b), respectively.

pleasantness rating, and experimental condition were considered for the analysis. We used the Linear Mixed Models to assess whether the stimulation modality (i.e., linear or rabbit) or the presence of vibration predicted the selected temperature and the pleasantness rating.

Results showed a statistically significant effect of the type of stimulation on the final temperature ($\beta = -1.3$, $t = -5.44$, $p < 0.001$), while the effect of the vibration was not statistically significant. In particular, participants preferred a temperature significantly lower in the rabbit stimulation (33.29 ± 3.97 °C) than in the linear one (34.59 ± 3.24 °C). Final temperatures at varying experimental conditions are reported in a boxplot representation in Fig. 3a.

As regards the pleasantness rating, there was a statistically significant dependence of perceived pleasantness on type of stimulation ($\beta = -0.99$, $t = -16.35$, $p < 0.001$) and presence of vibration ($\beta = 0.15$, $t = 2.44$, $p < 0.01$). On average, the linear stimulus was found more pleasant than the rabbit one (7.48 ± 0.77 and 6.49 ± 0.99 for linear and rabbit, respectively). Similarly, the presence of vibration was rated slightly more pleasant (7.06 ± 1.00) with respect to having no vibration (6.91 ± 1.03). Pleasantness ratings at varying experimental conditions are reported in a boxplot representation in Fig. 3b.

B. Experiment 2: Velocity

Final end-effector velocity, pleasantness rating, and experimental condition of each trial were considered for the analysis. A LMM analysis with modality and presence of vibration as fixed effects, and participant as random effect was performed on final end-effector velocity and pleasantness rating to assess whether there was a statistically significant relation.

As regards the final end-effector velocity, the LMM showed a significant dependence for the modality ($\beta = -0.005$, $t = -7.455$, and $p < 0.001$), and no effect for the presence of vibration. The mean selected velocity among the users in the linear modality was slightly higher (3.43 ± 0.10 cm s⁻¹) than for the rabbit modality (2.96 ± 0.50 cm s⁻¹). Results are depicted in Fig. 4a.

Similarly, when considering the pleasantness rating as dependent variable, results of the LMM analysis showed a significant effect for the modality ($\beta = -0.47$, $t = -10.5$, $p < 0.001$), and no effect for the presence of vibration. The linear modality (7.71 ± 0.68) was rated more pleasant than the rabbit one (7.25 ± 0.89). Outcomes of the experiment are visually reported in Fig. 4b.

IV. DISCUSSION

Results were consistent across the two experiments. In the first experiment, the velocity of the end-effector was set at 3 cm s⁻¹ and participants adjusted the temperature. Although the mean selected temperature among all the trials (33.9 °C) was in line with existing literature [7], a lower temperature was preferred in the rabbit condition. We found this significant difference between the two modalities also in the pleasantness rating, as the rabbit modality was found less pleasant than the linear stimulation. Regarding the vibration, the stimulation with vibration was rated as more pleasant than the one without vibration. In the second experiment we set the temperature of the end-effector at 34 °C using the results of the first experiment, and participants had to adjust the stimulation velocity. The mean of the selected velocity among all the trials was equal to 3.2 cm s⁻¹, but on average the rabbit condition was set on slower velocity. Like in the first experiment, the rabbit condition was also found as less pleasant than the linear stimulation. Concerning the vibration, a trend with a more pleasant rating for the presence of vibration was found, but this result was not statistically significant.

To sum up, the rabbit modality was set slower and at a lower temperature than the linear modality. About the vibration, our experiments highlighted a small effect on the pleasantness of the stimulation. The results of both experiments agree with the literature about the CT fibers, which pointed out their role in response to caress-like stimuli [8]. Indeed, these fibers respond better to stimuli with a temperature similar to the body temperature and a velocity around 3 cm s⁻¹. When they are stimulated with such a stimulus, a participative

Fig. 4: Results of Experiment 2. Final selected velocity and pleasantness ratings divided by experimental condition are reported in a) and b), respectively.

sense of pleasure is elicited in the person. Given the score of the pleasantness rating, we can conjecture that the CT fibers were also active during the rabbit stimulation. This hypothesis could be confirmed through a future study using the microneurography technique during the rabbit stimulation. Furthermore, the effect of the vibration is in line with the results of Israr and colleagues [9], in which they found that a lower frequency of stimulation (20 Hz) was evaluated as more pleasant than a higher frequency (250 Hz).

The results on the pleasantness of the stimuli are promising in the aim of simplifying the technology complexity while still maintaining a good quality of the stimulus. Indeed, even though the linear stimulation was found more pleasant than the rabbit one in both experiments, the ratings were not markedly discriminating between the two modalities. This is especially true in Experiment 2, where linear and rabbit mean ratings were 7.71 ± 0.68 and 7.25 ± 0.89 , respectively. It is worth mentioning that in this case the temperature was fixed at the mean favourite temperature of Experiment 1. On the contrary, in Experiment 1 there was a slight difference between the average favourite velocity retrieved from Experiment 2 (i.e., $3.20 \pm 0.83 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$) and the one fixed for the experiment (i.e., 3 cm s^{-1}), which could have influenced the perceived pleasantness of the stimulus. This hypothesis is strengthened by the lower ratings received by both modalities (7.48 ± 0.77 and 6.49 ± 0.99 for linear and rabbit, respectively) and their greater variability with respect to those of Experiment 2.

V. CONCLUSION

Nowadays haptic technology is not only a matter of digital touch realism, but also a novel opportunity to emotionally engage people in remote interactions. In this work we investigated how a caress-like stimulus provided with haptic technology should be adjusted (in terms of temperature and velocity) to obtain a comparable pleasant sensation when the stimulus is simplified from a continuous movement (linear) to a discrete sequence of taps (rabbit). Based on our knowledge, this was the first study on affective haptics in which participants adjusted

the stimulation as they preferred. Indeed, in similar studies reported in literature the parameters were set and kept constant throughout the whole experiment.

Results of our experimental campaign pointed out that, among the proposed caress-like stimuli, participants preferred linear movements set at 34.6°C and 3.4 cm s^{-1} . Anyway, a small decrease in the pleasantness ratings was observed for caress-like stimuli provided with discrete sequences of taps at 33.3°C and 3.0 cm s^{-1} . The presence of vibration had a little effect on the pleasantness ratings.

To conclude, our results provide the guidelines to scale down the technological complexity of affective haptics devices without altering the pleasantness of caress-like sensations. Further studies will be required in a wider range of stimuli and emotional states to establish a more general protocol allowing effective simplification of haptic signals.

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